

Net zero DRI scoping interim report: stakeholder feedback

Date: 21st July 2022

In attendance:

Stakeholders: Andrea Sharpe (NERC), Anna Angus-Smith (NERC), Richard Gunn (EPSRC), Lorna Smith (EPCC - University of Edinburgh), Peter Oliver (Technology Division in Scientific Computing Department, STFC), Adrian Hines (Head of JASMIN, STFC), Tom Griffin (Director of Scientific Computing Department, STFC).

Project team: Stephen Mobbs (PI for project, Head of National Centre for Atmospheric Science), Martin Jukes (Project lead), Ag Stephens, Charlotte Pascoe, Poppy Townsend, Jennifer Bulpett, Katie Cartmell, Sophie Mosselmans, Lucy Woodward

Apologies: Michele Weiland (EPCC - University of Edinburgh), Alan Simpson (EPCC - University of Edinburgh), Mark Parsons (Exascale project), Candice Snelling (NERC/UKRI)

Report Authors: Lucy Woodward, Poppy Townsend, Martin Jukes.

Reference this report: Woodward, L., Townsend, P., and Jukes, M.N., 2022:
Net zero DRI scoping interim report: stakeholder feedback (report on meeting held July 21st, 2022), Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.6962305, 2022

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

RAL Space

Harwell Campus

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NERC ([NE/W007134/1](#)).

Meeting overview:

This meeting was an opportunity to gather feedback from key DRI stakeholders about the interim report executive summary. During the 2-hour meeting, the project team asked the stakeholders to provide their thoughts and comments. The team provided a short overview presentation (see below) about the executive report and then invited discussion from the stakeholders.

The discussion was focused on the recommendations in the executive summary – these were summarised in a numbered table (see below) and then discussed verbally via numbered post-it notes on an interactive whiteboard (see below). The post it notes were ordered on two quadrant analyses diagrams to encourage the stakeholders to come to a collective decision about the recommendation's clarity, relevance, priority and difficulty. The meeting chair moved the post-it notes around the whiteboard based on the feedback and discussion in the meeting. The final placement is shown in the image below.

Key discussion points during the meeting:

- The project team explained how the recommendations largely fall under two headline messages: Consultation and Appropriate Procurement.
- The stakeholders asked if it was possible to quantify some of the recommendations so that we can prioritise. The discussion agreed that this would be very challenging, and in doing so we would waste time that could be used actually making changes. We need to act rather than deciding what to do first – the discussion reiterated the emphasis about how we are dealing with a climate emergency.
- Some recommendations were thought to be less clear (e.g. the ones in the lower half of the clarity quadrant analysis – see figure below)
- It was noted that the recommendations are at different levels and are for different audiences – the stakeholders suggested this should be addressed in the final report.
- It was reiterated about the importance of building consensus. The stakeholders recommended that workshops (with the purpose of gaining consensus) organised by the project should have clear outcomes at the end.
- Some of the recommendations can't be dealt with internally - we need collective action, in some cases globally.
- The project team emphasised that carbon offsetting should be explicitly a last resort, something done in conjunction with all other solutions. Discussion around the need to communicate this area well is very important to avoid any appearance of greenwashing.

The following specific points were raised and addressed in revisions to the interim report text prior to publication of the draft final version in August:

- Recommendation 3 wasn't clear if it was about leading the research or leading the activities to reach net zero.

- Recommendation 4 isn't specific enough
- Recommendations 5 and 6 are important but it isn't clear how they fit here
- Recommendation 7 should be made more explicit
- Recommendation 15 is difficult but high priority
- Figure 1 and 2 show the results of a prioritisation exercise in the meeting.

There was a short discussion on the user survey being prepared by the project. CP explains the user behaviour survey, what it is and why we're doing it (see slides for details). SM commented that the most important aspect is not the question but who you ask – hard to encourage the people you really want to do the survey to do it.

Appendix containing figures, tables and slides presented during the meeting

Figure 1: Quadrant analysis from the interactive whiteboard used during the stakeholder meeting. This analysis shows clarity vs relevance.

Figure 2: Quadrant analysis from the interactive whiteboard used during the stakeholder meeting. This analysis shows priority vs difficulty.

Table: A summary of the recommendations from the executive summary (as presented to the stakeholders on 21st July 2022). Note some of these have since been updated for the final report based on feedback from the meeting.

Recommendations	Themes
	Building Consensus
1	The UKRI DRI needs to ensure that investment decisions are backed by a deep understanding of the views of the research community.
2	UKRI should use its capacity in social, arts and humanities, and in economics, to understand the range of societal views , the avenues of consensus which open-up potential for accelerating transition and the emerging (or exploding) discords which can block or reverse change.
	Leading
3	Create a focal point which can bring together the strands of activities across the research sector to enable a coherent approach on the Net Zero DRI roadmap.
	Technology & Capability
4	The UKRI DRI needs to invest in the development of capability to deliver effective scientific throughput in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.
5	Steps must be taken to minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies arising from new technologies.
	User efficiency & Market Rebound
6	Ensure the introduction of new technologies is matched by appropriate resources for training and user support .
7	Ensure the procurement framework enables the conversion of efficiency gains into carbon savings .
	Electricity Supply
8	Best practice for an individual institution is to adopt 100% off-grid renewable electricity supply
9	Adoption of multi-year power purchase agreements with renewable investment clauses
10	Construction of grid-scale battery storage matched to the institutional power demands
11	Building on-site renewable generation and grid-connected power storage to mitigate load on the national
	Procurement of equipment
12	Institutions making purchases on behalf of UKRI must be empowered to balance investments in efficiency against investments in energy intensive infrastructure .
13	Add sustainability clauses in procurement contracts
14	Build relationships along the supply line to work on mutually beneficial solutions
15	Look at the whole life cycle of equipment and opportunities to extend the life and re-use potential of equipment.

	Estates and Travel
16	Fossil-free on-site operations should be established in the near term. There does not appear to be a need to wait for further information before setting a timeline for elimination by 2025 .
17	The UKRI DRI should facilitate and promote digital collaboration tools and awareness to reduce carbon intensity and enhance access to the research programmes.
	Offsetting, Sequestration and Biochar
18	UKRI needs to be exhaustive in exploring what can be avoided before, during, and after taking steps to deal with unavoided emissions.
19	Given uncertainty in the scalability of biochar and other carbon removal innovations, the UKRI need to couple investments with research into their sustainability.
20	UKRI should ensure that any offsetting investments are linked to guarantees of institutional continuity, e.g. through a trust.
	Wielding Impact
21	There is currently no requirement for researchers to consider that their research could have a negative impact on sustainability. The existential crises that face us in climate and biodiversity need to be reflected in every grant application as a key element of ethical and societal responsibility.
	Delivering the Net Zero DRI
22	The UKRI DRI must ensure continuity of activities which can assess best practice and deliver guidance to all those involved in funding, procuring, operating and using digital research infrastructure .

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Stakeholder Meeting

**UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure
Scoping Project**

21st July 2022

Agenda

Welcome / round table (5 mins)

Executive summary - intro slides (15 mins)

Reminder of project scope

Caveats and emerging themes

Creating tomorrow's research environment

Key recommendations from interim report

Feedback and discussion (40 mins)

User survey (including discussion – 40 mins)

Wrap up/next steps (15 mins)

Round Table

Brief introductions

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Executive summary – introduction (15 mins)

Martin

Climate Emergency and Transformational Change

- "We have a choice: **Collective action or collective suicide**" António Guterres, 18th July 2022
- "The science is unequivocal: a global increase of 1.5° C above the pre-industrial average and the continued loss of biodiversity risk catastrophic harm to health that will be impossible to reverse." Atwoli et al. 2021 [editorial published in 231 medical journals].
- 1.5° C is virtually impossible to avoid now; we are on track for 3° C or more .. "collective suicide"

Project Ambition

- Collect **evidence** to inform UKRI DRI Investment decisions
- Provide UKRI and their community with an **outline roadmap** for achieving carbon neutrality in their DRI by 2040 or sooner
- Enable UKRI to **play a positive and leading role** in the national and global transition to a sustainable economy

Timeline for key project outputs

Caveats and Emerging Theme

- We are looking at an 18-year* planning horizon – but the interim report does not set out a specific timeline.
- Many thousands of institutions around the world have been taking action to mitigate their climate impact for decades.
- There is a huge potential to learn from the experience of others.
- We can also learn from work on transformational change -- consensus should not be taken for granted and considerable effort is needed to build secure foundations for change.

* There is a significant chance that the net zero target (and the trajectory to "collective suicide") will be moved forward in time or replaced by other targets before 2040.

Headline 1: Consultation

Zetta-scale compute

An immersive system, combining Digital Twins, AI, Virtual Reality

Zero Carbon

Sustainable by design.

Generation Z

Designed for the researchers from Generation Z

Creating a Research Environment for Scientific Leaders

Headline 2: Appropriate procurement

- Balancing investments in efficiency against investments in energy intensive infrastructure will be crucial
- Procurement needs to reflect ambition for a central role in UK research
- Requirements on continuity and accessibility

Creating Tomorrow's Research Environment

- The DRI of 2040 will play a pivotal role in UKRI research programs.
- Artificial intelligence, virtual realities and digital twins running on zettascale platforms will transform the way in which we **explore the physical world and the human experience.**
- **The net zero lens** identifies the changes that we need to create a **Research Environment which matches societal ambitions for a sustainable and equitable society.**
- Adopting the recommendations of this report will bring substantial co-benefits through **co-design of the Digital Research Infrastructure, greater efficiency of research workflows, and reliable procurement.**

Key recommendation themes

1. Building Consensus
2. Leading
3. Technology and Capability
4. User Efficiency and Market Rebound
5. Electricity Supply
6. Procurement of Equipment
7. Estates and Travel
8. Offsetting, Sequestration and Biochar
9. Wielding Impact
10. Delivering the Net Zero DRI

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Feedback/discussion about the recommendations (40 mins)

Poppy

Feedback/Discussion

45 minutes to discuss and add comments to the Miro board.

Quadrant analysis:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVOlucJ5k=/?share_link_id=6911129880

(password = net-zero-dri)

Numbered recommendations:

[https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZtXvyhKgueA5PnC9BjFL-](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZtXvyhKgueA5PnC9BjFL-7hdfreE7d_IW9derCi9tAiU/edit?usp=sharing)

[7hdfreE7d_IW9derCi9tAiU/edit?usp=sharing](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZtXvyhKgueA5PnC9BjFL-7hdfreE7d_IW9derCi9tAiU/edit?usp=sharing)

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User behaviour survey (10 mins)

Charlotte

User Behaviour Survey

- A response to concerns about **lack of input from sectors** of the community that do not respond to meeting invites.
- To be run by a social scientist with experience in surveying attitudes on sustainability (Dr. Laura McGuire, Edgehill University).
- Including an assessment of **implicit attitudes to environmental sustainability**.
- Probe **motivations and barriers** to sustainable use of DRI.

Outcomes

- Better understanding of views across the user community.
- Engaging with social sciences to improve understanding of community attitudes.
- Inform policy recommendations.

Implicit Association Test

In collaboration with Laura McGuire:
Edge Hill consortium partner

Audience:

Science Support and Researchers

- Providers of Digital Infrastructure
- Users of Digital Infrastructure
- People who wouldn't necessarily describe themselves as users of digital infrastructure

How it works:

Computerised Sorting Task

Participants categorise a set of good and bad words and a set of high and low carbon items

Topics:

- Behaviour at Work
- Writing Code / Using Software
- Open Science
- Managing Data
- Rebound Effect
- Using Centralised DRI
- Buying / Disposing / Maintaining Kit
- Organising / Attending Events

We'd like your help to flesh out the questions about behaviours and attitudes related to the transition to net Zero DRI

Follow Up Questions

8 Pairs of Images

Low Carbon

&

High Carbon

User Survey Topics

- Behaviour at Work
 - Reducing environmental impact of the workplace
- Writing Code / Using Software
 - Look for efficiencies in software
- Open Science
 - Seek collaboration to avoid duplication – making data available via community standards
- Managing Data
 - Consideration of environmental impact of storing data
- Rebound Effect
 - Where efficiency savings lead to increased use of resources
- Value of Research
 - Is the work a "good" use of resources
- Use of Centralised DRI
 - What stands in the way of use of centralised services?
- Buying / Disposing / Maintaining Kit
 - Environmental impact of upgrading and the decommissioning of equipment – actions to extend life of kit
- Organising / Attending Events
 - Carbon emissions take precedence over costs

Example: Behaviour at Work

I turn lights off in the office when I leave the room

Always/Often/Sometimes

Rarely/Never

Yes	No
It saves energy	I always forget
It saves my company money	I share my office
I like to lead by example	It's not my responsibility
I would get into trouble if I didn't	Nobody else does it
I feel like I should because it's what everyone else does	I don't like my office to look unoccupied
Other:	Other:

Would you be willing to do this in the future?

YES/NO/MAYBE

Please give details in the box provided below:

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Feedback/discussion about the user survey (30 mins)

Charlotte

Feedback/Discussion

Add your thoughts:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVOlucJ5k=/?share_link_id=6911129880

(password = net-zero-dri)

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Wrap up (15 mins)

Poppy / Martin

Wrap up and next steps

Your feedback from today will be considered for the interim report (and final report).

Interim report will be submitted to NERC HO and published on our website soon.

Various graphics have been created to sit alongside (and within) the interim report. These will be used to disseminate the findings to a wider audience.

We will host a webinar to share and discuss the key recommendations with the wider community in September.

On 22nd September, we are also hosting a workshop with procurement stakeholders to gather information.

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Thank you

Get in touch: support@ceda.ac.uk

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Extra slides

1. Building Consensus

The UKRI DRI needs to ensure that investment decisions are backed by a deep understanding of the views of the research community.

The Net Zero target needs to be treated, like Health and Safety, as something that **concerns everybody** in the research sector. The response must reflect the recent recognition of a **climate emergency**.

UKRI should use its capacity in social, arts and humanities, and in economics, to understand the **range of societal views**, the avenues of consensus which open-up potential for accelerating transition and the emerging (or exploding) discords which can block or reverse change.

2. Leading

A focal point which can **bring together the strands of activities** across the research sector is needed in order to enable a coherent approach on the Net Zero DRI roadmap.

3. Technology & Capability

The UKRI DRI needs to **invest** in the development of capability to deliver effective scientific throughput in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

Steps must be taken to **minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies** arising from new technologies.

4. User Efficiency & Market Rebound

The UKRI DRI needs to ensure that...

- the introduction of new technologies is matched by appropriate **resources for training and user support.**
- the procurement framework enables the **conversion of efficiency gains into carbon savings.**

5. Electricity Supply

Best practice for an individual institution is to adopt **100% off-grid renewable electricity supply**, but this is only possible in a limited number of locations.

More general solutions:

- adoption of **multi-year power purchase agreements** with renewable investment clauses
- construction of **grid-scale battery storage** matched to the institutional power demands
- **building on-site renewable generation** and grid-connected power storage to mitigate load on the national grid.

6. Procurement of equipment

Institutions making purchases on behalf of UKRI must be **empowered to balance investments in efficiency against investments in energy intensive infrastructure.**

The carbon emissions associated with the manufacture of digital hardware are substantial and immediate measures need to be taken:

- **sustainability clauses in procurement contracts**
- **building relationships along the supply line** to work on mutually beneficial solutions
- looking at the **whole life cycle of equipment** and opportunities to extend the life and re-use potential of equipment.

7. Estates and Travel

Fossil-free on-site operations should be established in the near term. There does not appear to be a need to wait for further information before setting a timeline for elimination **by 2025**.

The UKRI DRI should facilitate and **promote digital collaboration tools** and awareness to reduce carbon intensity and enhance access to the research programmes.

8. Offsetting, Sequestration & Biochar

UKRI needs to be exhaustive in exploring **what can be avoided** before, during, and after taking steps to deal with unavoided emissions.

Best practice is to **adopt carbon offsetting now** and implement a plan to **transition to sequestration** before the net zero target date.

Given uncertainty in the scalability of biochar and other carbon removal innovations, the UKRI need to **couple investments with research** into their sustainability.

UKRI should ensure that any offsetting investments are linked to guarantees of institutional continuity, e.g. through a trust.

9. Wielding Impact

There is currently no requirement for researchers to consider that their research could have a negative impact on sustainability.

The existential **crises** that face us in climate and biodiversity need to be **reflected in every grant application** as a key element of ethical and societal responsibility.

10. Delivering the Net Zero DRI

The UKRI DRI must ensure **continuity of activities** which can assess best practice and **deliver guidance** to all those involved in **funding, procuring, operating and using digital research infrastructure.**